

Impolite Language Usage in African-American-Based TV Series

Omar Hazim Yaseen

General Directorate of Education Diyala

Iraq

Corresponding Email: Almahdawi.interpreting@yahoo.com

Abstract

People usually use impolite expressions to express their feelings towards something makes them angry. Especially, those who have bad temper all time. These expressions may use differently from culture to culture and from one person to another. This study is an attempt to investigate the impolite language usage in live TV shows. The study aims at examining impolite expressions through selected TV series realistically. The sample of the study consists of three TV series and the number of episodes surveyed reached 50. Thus, descriptive qualitative method was used in this study.

The data consisted of utterances within the context of dialogues spoken by TV-series characters. In this study, inductive technique was used to investigating the data. Triangulation was employed to increase the dependability and accuracy of the data and to establish trustworthiness. The model of analysis adopted in this study is Culpeper's (1996:88) which is categorized out of three main categories, types, realization and responses.

The findings of the study reveal that positive impoliteness is the most frequent used by speakers, while withhold politeness is the least frequent performed of impoliteness strategies in the addressees' utterances. Each type of impoliteness strategy has its particular realization. Also, the participants used the impolite language usage intentionally and instrumentally.

Keywords: Face Attack, Impoliteness, Impolite Language Usage, TV series

Introduction

In communication, there are numerous verbal acts called social rules known and used by people in a community. These rules are applied by society to illustrate what is the most appropriate and inappropriate spoken form. They reveal the essential and acceptable ways of managing things. In society, language is used as a form of communication and is restricted by social norms. However, language is utilized in society to uphold positive social interactions with others. Thus, individuals should follow social norms by exhibiting positive behavior or showing courtesy to accomplish this.

Socially, social norms restrict language usage as it is a tool for communication and good social interactions are maintained through positive language in society. It's crucial to strengthen interpersonal relationships and abide by social norms to promote harmony with others in the community through good behavior and polite actions. Conversely, linguistic strategies are employed to attack someone's face. Culpeper (2011:60) stated that their courteous acts are not intended to infringe on the identities or rights of others.

Generally, politeness can vary from culture to culture. A polite act in one culture may not hold the same meaning in another. For instance, when Japanese individuals meet their neighbours in

the street or when their neighbours pass in front of their houses, it is customary and seen as respectful to inquire about their neighbours' activities. Yet, for Americans, it may come across as impolite. While politeness is culturally relative, the universal need for good social interactions and harmony makes it important across cultures. People aim to be polite when using "please", "sorry", and "thank you", regardless of the culture.

Politeness is crucial in social interactions. It is unavoidable to violate it, which means being impolite. People can unknowingly or intentionally offend others through their words or actions. According to Bousfield and Locher (2008:36), Culpeper defines impoliteness as the use of communicative behaviour to cause the target to experience "face loss" or what the target perceives as such. It uses phrases like verbal abuse, bullying, threats, and similar tactics to hide itself. Today, it's considered a significant matter. Numerous scientific studies have shown verbal acts can be more harmful and destructive than physical ones.

Furthermore, researching impoliteness is crucial as it has significant social consequences and can severely harm personal lives. Nowadays, incivility is very noticeable in public life, particularly in the digital age. The media frequently reports on it, especially when it appears highly abnormal, such as when a congressman verbally abuses the president or verbal abuse leads to suicide. Moreover, it is forbidden on public signs, charters, and other legal documents.

Culpeper (1996:349-367) defines impoliteness as using power in certain situations to disrupt social order. There are different ways to do this, such as the speaker intentionally attacking the listener's face or the listener perceiving face attacks. In the selected TV series, the impoliteness strategy is a frequently used form of bad communication in dialogues. The live TV shows depict characters using impolite language in action. Surprisingly, people tend to comment more on rude, impolite, and discourteous behavior, even though they interact politely.

Understanding a community's language and sociocultural values is essential to speaking politely. Refrain from using words or language that causes discomfort to others. Informal situations typically involve impolite expressions used towards peers or ordinary people, which affects formality. So, being impolite while communicating enables individuals to get to know each other better in their personal lives. People are created in different genres, social backgrounds, and cultures, making it exceedingly necessary.

Cutting (2003: 52) notes that in certain cultures, the word employed is considered polite, while in others, it may be seen as impolite. The speaker needs to understand the culture of the audience. Thus, in cross-cultural communication, polite and rude expressions are heavily impacted. Cross-cultural communication can lead to misunderstandings caused by language differences. For instance, British instructors are not accustomed to receiving compliments from their students, unlike the Chinese, for whom it is a customary act of politeness. It's uncommon to find studies concentrating on pragmatics, particularly impoliteness strategies.

It's common for people to use impolite language usage in their daily spoken form. In addition, numerous TV series nowadays incorporate rude language in their dialogue. Some rude expressions were used by them recently. This study chose current TV series because they contain impolite language usage.

Impoliteness: An Overview

A considerable number of studies have been done lately on linguistic impoliteness. Scholars who have approached this matter from various perspectives have proposed different definitions

and models. Culpeper (1996:355) portrayed impoliteness as the antagonist of politeness and thus developed impoliteness strategies based on Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness theory.

The first scholar to discuss politeness was Culpeper (1996). Culpeper (2003: 1564) uses the term "impoliteness" to refer to "communication strategies aimed at attacking one's face, leading to social conflict and disharmony". Another scholar, Bousfield, argued that impoliteness was a deliberate attempt to attack someone's reputation rather than a failed attempt to be polite. The study of impoliteness has become one of the most interesting subjects to be explored recently.

According to Bousfield (2008:72), impoliteness refers to the intentional delivery of gratuitous and conflictive verbal face-threatening acts (FTAs). This is done either without mitigation in contexts where it is required, or with deliberate aggression to maximize the face damage inflicted.

The difference between politeness and impoliteness lies in the speaker's intention - whether they aim to attack face (impoliteness) or support face (politeness) (Culpeper, 2005: 140). Culpeper (1996:355) offers an impoliteness framework that corresponds but contrasts with Brown and Levinson's (1987:68) politeness theory, to address impoliteness. In summary, certain impolite actions cannot be overlooked in specific contexts, as they are a crucial part of the communication process.

Interface

Impoliteness with Intention

According to Bousfield and Locher (2008:3), impoliteness refers to behavior that upsets one's face in a specific setting. This definition requires further clarification. Impoliteness studies prioritize impoliteness that is intentional as the major component.

Bousfield (2008:66) and Culpeper (2005:80) stated that impoliteness is influenced by the speaker's intention and the hearer's ability to recognize these intentions. Whereas, according to Terkourafi (2008:42), as cited by Osmanovic (2018:16), an utterance can be deemed impolite by the hearer, even if the speaker did not intend for it to be so.

In Culpeper's (2005:72) developed definition, he highlights the importance of intention as the key and explains that the notion of face is central part to understanding offence. Identifying * intention is a difficult job, but communication can help (Mirhosseini, Mardanshahi & Dowlatabadi, 2017:20).

Impoliteness with Rudeness

While 'rudeness' can be described in many ways, researchers have identified a limited number of qualifiers for linguists and scholars to use. Rudeness, according to Rondina and Workman (2005: 3), is defined as anything that offends another person, causing discomfort or inconvenience due to something you say or do, or fail to say or do. While, Dubrin (2011:87) defined it as "a lack of regard for others" when someone engages in behavior that is insensitive or disrespectful.

However, according to Beebe (1995:159), rudeness can be described as a face threatening act (FTA) that contravenes a socially accepted norm of interaction in a given social context, which may include intonation. This statement was cited by Culpeper (2011:19). The definition's distinctive aspect is that it considers rudeness as both a personal and social offense.

Segarra (2007: 141) believes that rudeness is a deliberate act which conveys a message of indifference towards good social manners and intentional discourtesy. Unlike the definition of impoliteness, which occurs accidentally, rudeness is intentional. The definition of impoliteness, as stated by Culpeper (2005: 35), is when the speaker intentionally attacks the face, or when the hearer perceives such behavior as intentional face-attack, or both (cited in Bousfield and Locher (2008: 131)). The first point concerns impoliteness and its intention, while the remaining part of the definition highlights the opposite and uses the term 'or' to explain that the speaker does not intend to offend the listener but the latter misinterprets it as impolite behavior.

Terkourafi (2008: 68) suggests that impoliteness can be unintentional or intentional, depending on the listener's linguistic understanding, while rudeness is always viewed as deliberate (cited in Arendholez, 2013: 95). Impoliteness is used more frequently than rudeness, making it the secondary difference between them. Linguistics and communication are linked to impoliteness, while rudeness is connected to history in the humanities (Culpeper, 2011:79).

Impoliteness and rudeness are distinguished by Culpeper (2008: 31-2). Although both behaviors are deemed "Inappropriate and negatively marked," Culpeper suggests that impoliteness is deliberate while rudeness is not. Therefore, Culpeper believes that impoliteness is intentional.

Terkourafi (2008: 31-2) also makes a distinction between impoliteness and rudeness. This distinction contradicts Culpeper's definition. He claims that rudeness is a deliberate act, while impoliteness is not intended and his statement is based on Lexicography. Terkourafi (ibid) notes that rudeness in English dictionaries generally implies intention, while impoliteness refers to an unintended slight.

According to Bousfield and Locher (2008: 3), "face-aggravating behavior in a specific context" has a precise meaning. Lakoff brings up the impoliteness of a rude attitude. She suggests that rude behavior lacks expected politeness strategies and is intentionally negative and confrontational (Lakoff (1989: 103)).

Beebe defined rudeness as a face-threatening act that violates a socially sanctioned norm of interaction, including intonation, and utilized the term to refer to impoliteness (Beebe, 1995: 159). According to Culpeper (2003: 1546), the term impoliteness refers to communication plans that aim to attack one's face, leading to discord and debate.

Moreover, Rudenko, C. (2005:728) mentioned that there are two distinctions to analysis the intentions.

Overt and Covert Intentions.

1. Overt intention is a recognizable to the listener and the speaker intended to show it. On the contrary of that, covert intention is a hidden intention to the listener.

First-order and second-order intentions.

2. A first-order intention is an intention about the world. For its part, a second-order intention is an intention about a first-order intention (Ibid).

Types of Rudeness

In his book entitled "How to Become a True Professional" Segarra (2007:141) classifies rudeness":

- a) Rudeness of Word

It occurs when one uses street language, curses, interrupts others, tells dirty jokes, or asks personal questions to non-intimate people, which is considered a form of rudeness.

b) Rudeness of Action

This type refers to actions, both verbal and non-verbal, that are used to belittle and show contempt, such as ignoring others' feelings and opinions, being discourteous, or ignoring basic etiquette.

c) Inaction Rudeness

This category is focused on a person's inaction rather than their actions. It includes neglecting others while they speak, ignoring requests for help, and being apathetic and inattentive are all considered necessary behaviors to omit (Ibid).

Methodology

The current study combined the qualitative and quantitative methods to enhance and complete each other and to make this study richer and more comprehensive (Neuman, 2014:33).

The Model

This study used Culpepper's (1996) as an adopted model to investigate the impolite language usage functions which is performed by the participants in the selected African-American TV series.

The Sample

The study basically depends on African-American TV Series to analysis the impolite language usage. The sample consists of three popular TV series such as *Lovecraft Country*, *Godfather of Harlem*, and *The Chi*.

Data Collection and Description

The data of this study were adopted in the form of conversational scripts that included impolite language usage performed by the characters themselves in African-American TV series. The phenomenon is explained using real, unaltered data, based solely on the characters' reactions and without any constraints or misrepresentations.

Generally, to identify this phenomenon, a data source consisting of African-American TV series across multiple genres like drama, fantasy, horror, mystery, sci-fi, thriller, crime, and comedy was utilized. This study recognized three African-American TV series to analyze and extract impolite language usage such as "*Lovecraft Country* (2020)", "*Godfather of Harlem* (2019)", and "*The Chi* (2018)". The first TV series included one season, the second TV series have three seasons, and the last TV series comprised six seasons.

Normally, five episodes are randomly selected for each TV series. The timing of the selected shows varied from forty-five to sixty minutes. The total timing of the selected fifty episodes is two thousand and six hundred minutes. The selected TV series have been listed and defined as follows:

a) *Lovecraft Country* (2020)

It is an American TV series which podcasted on HBO in 2020. The genre of this TV series is horror drama and it's relayed on Matt Ruffs novel 2016. The story of this TV series is basically about a cross country traveler black man in the 1950s to look for his father and learn more about dark secrets.

b) *Godfather of Harlem* (2019)

It is an American TV series which is podcasted on Epix in 2019 and it is a crime drama TV series. It is about infamous crime boss who must take on an Italian family called Genovese to control back his neighborhood after ten years he spent in a prison.

c) The Chi (2018)

It is an American drama TV series has been acted on the south part of Chicago in 2018. It consists of six seasons. This TV series is about the local life of Chicago which presents the events in an unexpected way.

Data Analysis

Impolite language usage is totally analyzed according to Culpepper's model (1996) which is covered the types, realizations, and responses of impolite acts. However, data analysis can be defined as the way of arranging and organizing the data (Moleong 2007:280). This study utilized quantitative and qualitative methods as a combination to enhance the findings. The video of each episode of the sample was carefully watched and for reaching very adequate results the scripts of the episode were carefully read.

Findings

The process of analysis revealed the following findings. Table 1 shows the types of impolite language usage used by the participants.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of Impoliteness Strategies

NO.	Types and Realization of Impoliteness		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Bald and Record Impoliteness	Direct, Clear, and Unambiguous	44	9%
2.	Positive Impoliteness	Disassociating from Others	50	248 54%
		Calling the others Names	66	
		Utilizing Taboo Words	110	
		Using Inappropriate Markers	22	
3	Negative Impoliteness	Condescending, Scoring, and Ridiculing	28	81 17%
		Associating the other with a negative aspect explicitly	24	
		Invading the Other's Space	29	
4.	Sarcasm and Mock	Employing Insincere Politeness	38	8%
5.	Withhold Politeness	Being Silent	31	54 12%
		Failing to Thank	23	
Total			465	100%

According to the above table, impolite language usage occurred 465 times in the selected TV series. The five types of impoliteness and its realization are basically used by the main

characters.

In general, the first type, positive impoliteness, occurs 248 times (54%) in the forms of utilizing taboo words, calling the others names, disassociating from others, and using inappropriate markers. But, bald on record occurs 44 times (9%) in the form of direct, clear, and unambiguous realization. While, negative impoliteness occurs 81 times (17%) and expressed in the form of invading the other's space, condescending, scoring, and ridiculing, and associating the other with a negative aspect explicitly. The other type of impoliteness strategies that is occurs 38 times (8%) is called sarcasm and mock and it is performed in the form of employing insincere politeness. Additionally, withhold politeness occurs 54 times (12%) in the form of being silent and failing to thank.

As stated in Table 1, positive politeness ranked in the first place and it is followed by bald on record in the second. Sequentially, negative impoliteness ranked in the third place, withhold politeness took place in the fourth place, and sarcasm and mock came in the last place, and it comes as the most used type.

On the other hand, Table 2 shows the frequency and the percentage of the responses to the impolite language usage.

Table (2) Frequency and percentage of Responses to Impoliteness Strategies

N O.	Responses to Impolite language usage		Types of impoliteness Strategies												
			Bald and Record Impoliteness		Positive Impoliteness		Negative Impoliteness		Sarcasm and Mock		Withhold Politeness		Total		
			F	P	F	p	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P	
1.	Accepting the Face		22	21	40	31	2	24%	2	27	1	25	12	26%	
2.	Counter ing the Face	Offensi ve	18	17	35	27	3	34%	1	21	2	35	12	23	51
		Defens ive	35	33	22	17	2	26%	2	28	1	18	11		
3.	No Response		30	29	33	25	1	16%	2	24	1	22	11	23%	
Total			10	100	13	100	9	100	8	100	6	100	46	100%	
			5	%	0	%	1	%	2	%	0	%	8		

As shown in the Table 2, all the types of responses are used by the participants in the selected TV series. Generally, there are mainly four types of responses to impolite language usage such as accepting the face, countering, and no response. The most dominate type is countering face which is occurred 232 times (51%). Secondly, accepting the face type is used 116 times (25%) and no response type ranked as the third type with 110 times (24%).

Discussion

In the present study a number of frequencies and ways of impolite language usage responses have been dealt with and analyzed. The process of analyzing the data provides us a different result so they will be summarized accurately and then will be discussed.

The findings shows that all types and realizations of impoliteness strategies are performed by the participants in the selected TV series such as positive impoliteness, bald on record, sarcasm, or mock politeness, negative impoliteness, and withhold politeness. Nevertheless, the occurrence of impolite language usage differs in every TV series.

The data analysis showed that positive and negative impolite language usage are the most frequently performed by the TV series participants. While withholding politeness and sarcasm and mocking are least used by them. In the *Godfather of Harlem* TV series, the African-American criminal boss Bumpy Johnson faced frustrated, nasty, and annoyed hate speech by other bosses. He stayed in jail for ten years and went through difficulties. When he exited prison, he found his neighborhood was conquered by those bosses. This situation forced the main character to use taboo language almost in every part. The main participants utilized imposing somebody's freedom of action, ridiculing, not treating the other seriously, condescending the other person, explicitly associating the other with a negative aspect, etc. The discrimination and the impeded by others restricted his freedom. However, many participants used negative impolite words to undermine others through unfavorable aspects and personalizing them with negative aspects.

Furthermore, the *Chi* TV series showed the life of six teenagers in southwest Chicago. Brandon is a dreamed, confident and ambitious young boy who aims to open a modern restaurant someday, but he struggles between the responsibilities of his mother and brother and his new life. This allowed the main character to use impolite words to express his feelings towards the problems and responsibilities. On the other hand, in the *Lovecraft Country* TV series. A young man called Atticus Freeman went around the States with his girlfriend and uncle to find his missing father. They have to overcome the racism of American white people and the malevolent spirit. The main participants have repeatedly performed positive and negative impoliteness expressions.

The performed characters treated others in the form of positive impoliteness by screaming, belittling the other person, being unconcerned and unsympathetic, allying with other name, ignoring, denying common ground with other, etc. The selected TV series presents the use of taboo language. Generally, the high occurrence of impolite language usage is due to the limited positive and negative strategies, which have numerous sub-strategies.

Considering the participants' intentions, the three selected TV series showed that they performed impoliteness in their speeches, intentionally offending and attacking the addressees. Therefore, the

impoliteness phenomenon is instrumental and intentional. Moreover, the findings present that the TV series participants intentionally used rudeness to accomplish their long-term objectives. This statement aligns with Lakoff's [1989] assertion that impoliteness can be used to attack the other's face and achieve a specific purpose.

According to the responses, there are three types of responses which are performed by the participants in the TV series: accepting face attack by agreeing or apologizing, countering face attack offensively or defensively, and no response. This study is in line with Bousfield (2008) that participants repeatedly used strategies of defense to deal with this type by avoiding the conflict or by reducing the face damage. For example, the participants show their responses when they mocked or ridiculed by others. Additionally, if the listener responds to the speaker's impolite language with a friendly attitude, they are not attempting to challenge the speaker's dignity but they instead protecting their own by using defensive strategies.

Finally, this study also focused on the participants' responses toward impoliteness and showed that when the participants face a rudeness situation, they have two choices: responding or keeping silent. Based on the participants' facial expressions, the attached findings revealed that all participants understand the impoliteness strategies and most of them respond to these expressions and others lost their words to do the same.

Conclusions

The current study reached the following conclusions:

1. The participants intentionally and instrumentally used the impoliteness strategies.
2. African-American participants show the need to use the taboo words.
3. Five types of impolite language usage are performed by the characters in the selected TV series: Bald on Record, Positive Impoliteness, Negative Impoliteness, Sarcasm and Mock, and Withhold Politeness. Positive impoliteness is the most frequently used in these TV series.
4. Three types of responses are applied: Accepting the Face, Countering the Face Attack, and No Response. Countering the face is repeatedly performed more than others.
5. Offensive response is used by the participants more than defensive response
6. Regarding TV series, the participants of *The Chi* (2018) used the impolite expressions more than the two other TV series.

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